

The Venerable U SÝla, the founder of the Kyakhatwine Pariyatti PÜli University in Bago

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Abstract

The Kyakhatwine Pariyatti PÜli University is a center of trainers of trainee for the Pariyatti SÜsanÜ in Buddhism in today. Nowadays after 150 years old Kyakhatwine Pariyatti PÜli University becomes prosperous with full of buildings & educated monks being conducted doctrinal practice (Pariyatti) insight meditation. (Paáipatti). It is called Kyakhatwine as there have surrounded Kyakhat bamboos with thorns. Since 1226 ME, the ceremony of forest invitation (Tora PavÜraãÜ) was held. In 1233 ME, the ceremony of Kyakhatwine vinaya recitation had commenced. It has been recognized as the Shwekyin forest sect (Shwekyin Tora gaãa) or Shwekyin forest group (AraããavÜsÝ Shwekyin NikÜya) from the original forest sect (MPla Tora gaãa) up today. The famous Kyakhatwine forest monastery was founded by Ven. U SÝla, the first foremost forest dweller of the original sect AraããavÜsÝ mPlagaãa.

Introduction

The Kyakhatwine Pariyatti PÜli University is the 150 years old famous monastery as it was founded in 1226 ME (1864) in Bago City where the Teachings of the Buddha mostly flourished. The founder was the Venerable U SÝla who had lived by the Vinaya. He was the leader of the forest sect (MPla Tora Gaãa). Later the Shwekyin NikÜya and the AraããavÜsÝ gaãa combined into one group which became recognized as AraããavÜsÝ Shwekyin NikÜya. As the University was surrounded with the Kyakhat bamboos, it has been called Kyakhatwine.

The auspicious Kyakhatwine Pariyatti PÜli University is situated at the north-west of Bago city. The extent (acre) is 5.095. There stand about 40 buildings where 700 monks lived. They live there following the Vinaya rules, holding the Vinaya recital and invitation ceremony. The Venerable U SÝla who was eminent as an Arahat had founded together with his teacher, the KalyÜnÝ forest dweller the Venerable U Vaããa as they had the same desire, it is now 150 years old. This University is traditionally the main centre of (AraããavÜsÝ Shwekyin NikÜya Sect) the five districts: Bago, Kava, Vo, Dike U and Thanatpin and there was a saying is "the origin of forest sect is U SÝla."

Ven. U SÝla (1194-1269 ME)

Birth

The Ven. U SÝla was the founder of the Kyakhatwine University. The future U SÝla was born at 8 am, on Friday, the 8th waxing of Nataw, in 1194 ME. His birth village was the upper Zineganine 2 miles far away from the north of Bago. His parents were the merchant. U Tun Aung and Daw Cho. Among the five children, he was the eldest son. His child name was "Mg Shwe Thar". His grandfather was a royal servant. However he came down to the lower Myanmar being kept secret of his virtue and he earned his living by trading when he reached Zineganinegyi. While his mother was pregnant, she desired to observe the precepts and to eat vegetables. The future

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Sayadaw was afraid of doing evil actions. He used to look after the cattle and collect the grass for them. He used to share his materials to his friends. Some of his friends reviled him but he did not take revenge and he was patient to others. He played just like a monk.

Hovicehood & Monkhood

When he was ten years, his parents entrusted him to Phonedawgyi U Mhue to make a novice. There he educated as some knowledge for a child. When he was twelve years in 1206 ME, he became a novice by the name of Shin SÝÜcÜra. He did not go back home while he stayed as a lay man. He used to do duties of the monastery. In the month, Tapotwe, 1203 ME, he was ordained as a full-fledged monk in the Khaããa Chapter house being make Phonedawgyi of PÝlakhat village as his preceptor. His title was also U SÝÜcÜra. He learnt the Buddhist scripture under the Phonedawgyi U Mhue of Kopyin village for 2 years as a student, 7 years as a novice and 2 years as a monk. When he got 2 vassas, he transferred to Phoneyi Pun (a) U CandÜlaßkÜra and there he learnt Buddhist scriptures for 5 years. He was devoted by the people as he could preach well.

Religious Services

When he got 5 vassas, he transferred to Pazuntaung, Taunglonepyan, Shwekyetyet (Kyaitthiyae monastery) U MedhÜ and there he learnt Buddhist scripture for one year. After 6 vassas as a monk, he stayed in Bago under the KalyÜãÝ Phonedawgyi, the forest dweller U Vaããa and there he studied Buddhist scripture for one year. When he got 8 vassas, he studied Buddhist scripture at the eastern monastery, MahÜdhammikÜrÜma calintaik of Mandalay for one year. When he got 9 vassas, he came back his native land as he was not very well. He stayed in the villages LÜkamoe, Kyaitpadaingkonetan and Gþkone etc. as a forest dweller. He did not stay at the monasteries but he stayed at the cemeteries. Afterwards he stayed in the forest 5 furlongs far away from the village. In 1228 ME, he stayed together with his teacher Phoneyi Pun in Haãsakone forest. From the time when he got 15 vassas, he stayed in the forests being taken the practice living in the forest (Araããakadhutaßga). He stayed in the forests for so many vassas uncounted. He did not stay at one place but he wandered everywhere for his practices. Therefore the forest sect might be spread in every places. He was about 5.5 and he was white and slim. Among the four postures, he used a little sleeping.

Ven. U SÝla propagated the teachings of the Buddha without hesitation. He went everywhere when he was invited. He followed the rules of vinaya without any offence. He was secret in the insight meditation from others. He had a desire to come out Pariyatti centres in every places. He encouraged the monks to take a forest practice and the young monks to educate Buddhist scriptures. He used to travel alone or sometimes he was accompanied with a follower. He used to travel on foot. After 70 years, he used the stretcher or train. He was honoured with the shawls or turbans. So it is used to say that his feet were not touched with the earth.

From that time onwards when he got 12 vassas, he always observed 10 or 11 ascetic practices. Sometimes he observed 13 dhutaßgas and especially Paãsakþlika dhutaßga. Everywhere he arrived, he was not familiar with the monks or lay people and he gave short admonishment. He used to preach to abstain from killing, stealing

because it was leading to hell. And he told them that if one planted the mango tree which would bear sweet fruit and if one plant a neem tree which would bear bitter fruit. He preached them to take faith in three true jems.

In the BahudhÜtuka Sutta of UparipaãÜsa, it is said “that danger does not exist in noble person, it exist in evil person so that there is no danger for the noble person.” Ven. U SÝla was endowed with morality, concentration and wisdom. There were so many wonderful events concerning with him. He stayed in the forest all of his life so there was no forest in which he had not been. In the jungle there lived fearful and dangerous animals but for him they were friends. They kept away when they met with Ven. U SÝla. Petas, spirits and other beings came to him to preach the dhamma and offered him medicine in the guise of human beings. If he passed under a tree, the tree-spirit could not stay on the tree as it was very hot. The guardians of treasure came and supplicated to establish diamond and emerald pagodas. It is to believe that he was able to know the other’s intention. He could not be shot. He could not be conquered by the enemies. There came out water when it was pointed. These events were very wonderful.

The Ven. U SÝla stayed in the forest and observed dhutaßga. However he encouraged the Teachings doctrinal (pariyattisÜsanÜ) as it was the basic of the dispensation. So he urged to established the learning centre. According to this higher vision, he accepted the monasteries offered and made them great monasteries for learning centres. He also entrusted them to the persons who were able to control the monastery. He had established 9 monasteries. Among them, this Kyakhatwine was the first and foremost Buddhist University.

The Ven. U SÝla wandered the places whatever he desire to stay. In 1255 ME, he built a monastery on the land donated by U Pho Thant from Myenikone in Thaton and assigned U Dhammissara to preside the monastery. Now that monastery was famous as “DhammikÜrÜma Sarhintaik”. In 1256 ME, he kept his vassa in the Saikalay forest lodging at the south corner of Shwekyin city, Nyaunglaypin. After the rains-retract, monks from all places came to worship him. Then he assigned the Phoneygi U Soma of Khaweitara to stay at Nyaunglaypin. In 1256 ME, on the Wednesday, 3rd waxing of Tazaungmone, he went to Nyaunglaypin forest monastery accompanied with 11 monks and U Soma. On the Friday, 8th waxing day, he designated the chapter house. Afterwards he went to Belu Island, Mawlamyine City, he designated the chapter house on the 11th waxing of Tangu at the monastery of Ven. GandhamÜ. While he was staying in Mawlamyine, the donar U Tha Nyo and people donated him the Pabeitantaik monastery. As it was owned by the Saãgha, he entrusted it to the Ven. Mudum Sayadaw who assigned his pupil Ven. Bhaddiya to teach the scriptures as a lecturer. In that monastery, the recitation ceremonies of all sects were held yearly.

In 1260 ME, the donors from Kyaiktho wanted to invite him. So they sent a Chinese who bred the pigs, Ko Thwar to the Belu Island. He requested the Ven. U SÝla to stay at Kyaiktho for the compassion upon him who would abandon the evil actions. The Ven. U SÝla took his confession not to earn his living by selling all intoxicated materials and returned to Kyaiktho. There he stayed on the Seikphutaung forest lodging. U Thwar constructed a monastery being discussed his wife Daw Phau. With special regard to the donor U Thwar, he observed 5 rain-retreats there.

In 1262 ME, Thidingyut, the Kyaitkasan trustee U Thar Hman discussed with U Pho Nyien, the owner of Pyigyimaãaine and Setsan U Pho Thwin and the brick monastery was built on the land of west Kyaitkasan pagoda. They invited Ven. U SÝla

and donated it to him in the month of Pyarho. The Ven. Sayadawgyi accepted it and transferred it to the MahÜvisuddhÜruâ Sayadawgyi. That Sayadawgyi took Ven. U Uttama who was staying at Kyaik Padine Theinkone, (later he became the second Sayadaw of Kyakhatwine University) made him administer the monastery. In 1262 ME, Pyarho, Ven. U SÝla went to the Yankin forest monastery on the other shore of Nyaungdone, and there he consecrated the chapter house. Then the citizens were devoted him and invited him to accept their honour. The Ven. Sayadawgyi replied that if there were benefits for the dispensation, he would come there. The lay devotees arranged the places for monastery and chapter house and invited him to honour the consecrated ceremony of the chapter house in the waxing of Tabaung. The Ven. U SÝla travelled to Nyaungtone on Friday, in the 12th waxing of Tabaung 1262 ME accompanied with 55 monks by ship. On the 13th and 14th waxing of Tabaung, he removed the old chapter house and on the fullmoon day of Tabaung, they consecrated the chapter house. On the 1st waning day, the Sayadaws such as VisuddhÜrÜma Sayadaw returned. The Ven. U SÝla stayed there for 10 days and went back having assigned the duty of the monastery to the Sayadaw of KyaungtawrÜ monastery.

In 1267 ME, Pyarho, he went to the south of Shwekyin City, Tankhonting village and there consecrated the chapter house at the monastery of Sayadaw TejosÜra. He went to Nyaunglaypin on the 8th waxing morning of Pyarho and on that day he went by Yangon-Mandalay white train in one day for Uktwin. The 8th waxing, Monday of Pyarho, 1267 ME was the first day for the Sayadawgyi to take the train. He stayed for 5 days Uktwin, 3 days each at the corner monastery of Taungoo and Yokuttara Theinkone monastery. From Taungoo, he went to Phyu city and stayed there for three days. The donors such as U Ngwe and U Pyu supplicated him that they wanted to devote a monastery of the Sayadawgyi. So he assigned to Ven. U Soma to do the duties. So there appeared the two monasteries South Shwekyin and North Shwekyin in Phyu. Then he continued to Kanyutkwin and stayed there for 3 days. At that time his age was coming into 74 years. Then he continued to Peingwekone for 3 days. At Peingwekone forest monastery, on Tuesday, 14th waxing of Tapotwe, 1267 ME, he consecrated the chapter house. Then he arrived at Nyaunglaypin on Thursday, the 1st waning of Tapotwe, 1267 ME, on the 2nd waning day, he honoured a ordination ceremony. In this way, he went to Nyaunglaypin for the 3rd time and stayed for 3 days. He travelled according to the village, he arrived at Bago in the month of Tabaung. While he was staying at Leikpyarkan monastery in Bago Pakhan Sayadawgyi from upper Myanmar came and met with him by voyage. He worshipped the Ven. Pakhan Sayadawgyi to admonish him as he had taken the train. All the people who saw him devoted much just like, an Arahant near the Buddha image statue requesting the Pakhan Sayadawgyi.

The monks of Bago requested him not to go to the places invited as he became old. He replied that he could not be patient as he took pity on them. In 1268 ME, he took his last vassa at the Belu Island Kwanthe forest monastery. At the end of vassa, he went to Thaton and he honoured the Karen peasants of different religion on the mountain "VandÜmi", near of Gau village and Winsein village. They told him that they were very late to see the Sayadawgyi. If they saw him early, they would not take that religion. They accepted his admonishment respectfully. Afterwards, he consecrated the Chapter houses of Pantanaw district, Minkharu, U Ketu of Vovo village, U PaââÜ of Inma village, Pantanaw Seikgyi Sayadaw and Khaywekhapo village accordingly. He was very earnest in the work of consecrated chapter houses. But his health slowly

decreased. Then he performed the consecration and ordination ceremonies at Theinkone of 12 villages. From there he went to the cities Nyaungtone, Sale, Kwanthrepin and Dhanupyu accordingly and honoured them. The last to be consecrated monastery was SussÜna monastery in Zalon city.

Death

From Dhanupyu to Zalon, all devotees expected him all day. But the returned ship engine had breakdown and he had to stay there Dhanupyu. At 8 from, instead of the returned ship by the name of Nibhan arrived in. There was coincidence with the Nibhan ship and Zalon, the place for the Sayadawgyi to enter parinibbÜna. On the 3rd waning of Kason, 1269 ME, at 2 o'clock mid night, the Nibhan ship arrived in Zalon honour. Over 2000 people welcomed him. At that night U Pu's puppet theatre performance was to be stopped because the audience went to welcome the Sayadawgyi. The Sayadawgyi of SussÜna monastery supplicated him to take a rest for 2 or 3 days. But he replied that the self aggregate was not governed so that it was to consecrate hastily. Thus the consecrated ceremony of the chapter house was finished on Sunday, the 3rd waning of Kason, before meal. The Sayadawgyi recited the KammavÜcÜ lastly. It can be seen that he took the faith of the dispensation giving his life.

On Sunday, the 3rd waning of Kason, he was fine all day. At night he had to suffer from dysentery. He rejected all medicine. When the robe became dirty, it was taken to exchange another robe. But he did not let it. So they supplicated that the exchanged robe was already dotted by mark (kappabindu). So they exchanged the robe twice. He had not faint or became unconscious. At 7 o'clock, on the Sunday morning, the 4th waning of Kason, 1269 ME, he abandoned the burden of the aggregate and passed away peacefully. At that time he was 75 years old. He did not want to die in the city but he desired to die in the forest. According to his desire, he died at the SussÜna monastery in the Zalon. The worldly monks and lay people shed tears. They wept severely. However those people, devas and brahmas who knew clearly the dhamma of passing away recognized happily his death. There appeared a heavy earth quake, clamorously in the form of potter's wheel just like honouring the death of the Sayadawgyi. The SussÜna monastery is housed near the south the Zalon returned backhome image. Now there is another monastery, DhammikÜrum. There two are divided with fence. The news was sent by wireless and all of the people from Yangon, Bago and Mawlamyine were very much worried and cried heavily on hearing the parinibbÜna of the Sayadawgyi. The Sayadawgyi was requested to lie down the burden of the aggregate in the city because it was not worth to lie down in the small city. But he rejected to carry to the town. They decided to perform the fine ceremony in the month of Tapotwe. They built a residence for the remains of the Sayadawgyi accept the honour. Flowers, fruits such as mangos and coconuts were bearing inappropriate time wonderfully.

The funeral ceremony was held on the month of Tapotwe in 1269 ME. On that day it was very crowded but there was no quarrel, stealing and danger. The remains of the Sayadawgyi became non-state. As it was gilded, it became like a gold stone. It was arranged to cremate on the 2nd waning of Tapotwe. However it took the time as the songs for longing the Sayadawgyi was liked very much. So it was cremated at 8 o'clock, on the 3rd waning. The remains were fired on the pile of woods with perfume. As there were many people, who honoured the Sayadawgyi, perfume could not

bought in the bazaar of Zalon and Hansata. There left about 5 carts of sandal wood having created. The association of cremation allowed the people to take whatever they like after collecting the relics in the box. The people took ashes and other materials. Some took earth on which the cremation was held. Later they became ball relics from which radiation came out. In the cemetery, sometimes the great fire balls were seen flying in the sky at night. So that place was crowded daily. On the month of Tabuang, over 70 banners were staked and there held alms-offering ceremony. It was more crowded than the funeral ceremony. On the month of Kason and Nayun, the cart-road was closed and farm works were stated, the crowd left the place. The bones of the Sayadawgyi were pounded besmeared with lacquer and made two images of the Buddha measuring 12 inches in the height. One image was put in the bronze box enshrined it in the pagoda built at the forest monastery between Thamarokya village and Shwepankone village. The rest image was enshrined in the pagoda at the place where the cremation ceremony was held. That was called U Sýla pagoda. In addition, Khayewe mountain pagoda and the burial urn pagoda of Ukkan village were built.

Conclusion

If the arahats are ordinary arahats (Sukkhavipassaka), they left bones just like the ordinary person. If they made determination, there would be left relics their decision. In Myanmar in the dispensation of the Buddha, there were little eminent sayadwas as arahats: Ven. U Sýla, Ven. U Kavinda (a) Phonedawgyi U TharShwun and Mokout Sayadaw etc. The said Sayadawgyis were arahats who obtained higher supernormal power. So for those who had obtained privilege to honour then had satisfaction. The Ven. U Sýla had founded many monasteries beginning from the Kyakhatwine. But he made effort for the meditation staying in the forest. So Ven. U Sýla should be appreciated to be a noble Sayadawgyi endowed with Pariyatti and Paátpatti. In the history of Buddhism in Myanmar, the Ven. U Sýla was a famous Sayadawgyi who upgraded the development of Pariyatti and Paátpatti teaching of the Buddha.

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